

Analytical Applications of *N*-Haloamines and *N*-Haloamides for the Determination of some Sulphur containing Functional Groups

ASHUTOSH SRIVASTAVA* and SAMEER BOSE

Department of Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur

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A titrimetric procedure has been described for the determination of mercaptans and xanthates with a variety of *N*-haloamines and *N*-haloamides in the presence of potassium iodide. Mercaptans are titrated in dilute acetic acid whereas xanthates in bicarbonate medium. Determination of xanthates has been applied to determine carbon disulphide, involving conversion to xanthate by alcoholic hydroxide. The accuracy and precision both were found to be $\pm 0.5\%$ in each case.

DESPITE a bewildering variety of oxidizing agents known to the analytical chemists relatively few have been explored sufficiently to determine their degree of selectivity towards thiol groups. Since oxidation may occur by a variety of mechanism, it is not unreasonable to expect that significant differences in the reactivity of functional groups will be observed and that the orders of reactivity will differ. This variability is due first to differences in specificity of the reagent employed and secondly, because of the extents up to which it can stoichiometrically oxidize the sulphhydryl group. As a part of a project on the determination of sulphur containing organic compounds via their functional groups, reactions of *N*-haloamines such as monochloramine, dichloramine, monobromamine and dibromamine, and of *N*-haloamides such as *N*-bromobenzamide, *N*-chlorobenzamide, *N*-bromoacetamide and *N*-chloroacetamide with mercaptans and xanthates were investigated to evolve methods for the analysis of these sulphur functions. It has been observed that mercaptans are quantitatively oxidized to the corresponding disulphides with these oxidizing agents in the presence of acid and potassium iodide, the end point being noticed by the blue colour of starch-iodine. Xanthates were similarly titrated by using *N*-bromobenzamide and *N*-bromoacetamide as model oxidizing agents but no acid was added. The oxidation observes the following course consuming one mole of the oxidizing agent for two sulphur function.

Carbon disulphide was determined involving treatment with potassium ethoxide followed by titration of the ethyl xanthate formed.

Experimental

Reagents and Samples :

0.025M solution of *N*-haloamines¹⁻³ and those of *N*-haloamides⁴⁻⁶ were prepared by dissolving with

stirring an appropriate amount of each compound in distilled water, filtering off the insoluble residue and diluting suitably. *N*-chloroacetamide was dissolved in 2*N* sulphuric acid. These solutions were standardised iodimetrically.

Most of the mercaptan samples were used as received from M/S Evans Chemetics New York. Some of the mercaptan samples and all xanthates⁷ were prepared and purified by the authors. Carbon disulphide and all other samples were of C. P. grade.

Procedure :

Method for the Determination of Mercaptans and xanthates :

A Sample containing 0.1-1.0 m mole of mercaptan or potassium or sodium salt of xanthate was weighed into a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask and dissolved in 30-50 ml of water. Water-insoluble mercaptans were first dissolved in 10 ml of glacial acetic acid and then sufficient amount of water was added to keep the acid concentration about 30% v/v. Approximately 100 mg of potassium iodide and 1 ml of 1% starch sol. were added; 5 ml of 20% hydrochloric acid was also added when mercaptans were being determined. This was titrated with a 0.025M solution of oxidizing agent. In case of xanthates about 2 g. of sodium hydrogen carbonate was added. A blue colour of starch-iodine serves to detect the end point.

Precipitation of dixanthogens and some of the disulphides, does not hamper the reaction nor the end point. The contents should be shaken vigorously during the course of titration.

Method for Determining Carbon-di-sulphide :

A sample containing 0.1-1.0 m mole of carbon-disulphide was weighed in a small sealed glass bulb and placed in a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask having 0.5-2.0 ml of potassium ethoxide and 5 ml of absolute alcohol. The bulb was broken and the contents were swirled for 2 minutes. The flask was cooled in an ice-bath and 30 ml of water and 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator

* 171, Bhaldarpura Jabalpur, M.P.

was added ; it was titrated with 1M acetic acid solution until the contents were acid to indicator. The potassium ethyl xanthate was titrated with *N*-bromobenzamide or *N*-bromoacetamide using the general method described for xanthates.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 and 2 summarise the results for the determination of several mercaptans with *N*-haloamines and *N*-haloamides. Recoveries found by titration with each oxidizing agent are compared with those obtained with existing methods. Table 3 summarises the results obtained for the estimation of xanthates and carbondisulphides with *N*-bromobenzamide and *N*-bromoacetamide ; each of the result is compared with iodimetric assay^{13,14}. In Table 4 titration results are given that were studied in the presence of various foreign substances. The compounds chosen to study the effect include compounds that cause interference in other methods and compounds that contain other

sulphur functions. Hydrogen sulphide and thiocarbonyl compounds interfere severely.

No acid should be present when xanthates are being titrated since they decompose in acid medium. In neutral medium recoveries are quantitative. Mercaptans should be titrated in presence of acid ; in neutral medium about 2% high results are noticed.

The present study reveals that a variety of *N*-haloamines and *N*-haloamides can successfully be used for the selective and stoichiometric oxidation of a large number of mercaptans and xanthates. It appears that various alkyl substituted chloramines can also be used similarly. Albeit few anomalies were also observed. Mercaptans having a carboxyl group to the thio function over oxidize vitiating the analytical accuracy. Examples are, cysteine, mercapto succinic, 3-mercaptopropionic and *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid. It is probably the β -carboxyl group which forms a cyclic intermediate that overoxidizes from one titration to another in an unaccountable fashion⁸.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH *N*-HALOAMINES

Sample	MC*	DC*	MB*	Purity%		Ref
				DB*	Comparison Method	
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	98.2	98.0	98.2	98.4	98.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
1-Propanethiol	93.9	93.7	94.0	93.0	94.0	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Glutathione	98.2	98.0	98.4	98.6	98.2	Iodimetry (10)
Mercaptoacetic acid	82.2	82.0	82.3	82.1	82.5	Iodimetry (12)
2-Mercaptoethylammonium chloride	98.0	97.9	98.2	98.3	98.4	Iodimetry (12)
1-Pentanethiol	82.2	82.0	82.4	82.3	82.5	Acetylation (11)
2-Naphthalenethiol	99.0	99.0	99.2	99.3	99.5	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Thiobenzoic acid	95.2	95.0	95.1	95.3	94.9	Iodimetry (12)
1-Butanethiol	99.2	99.0	98.9	98.4	99.4	Acetylation (11)
Methyl-3-Mercaptopropionate	96.2	96.4	96.5	96.1	96.2	Iodimetry (12)
Allyl thiol	94.0	93.7	94.0	93.9	94.1	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Benzenethiol	99.1	98.8	99.0	98.9	99.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Toluene- α -thiol	98.6	98.3	98.6	98.4	98.7	Acetylation (11)
2-Mercaptoethanol	97.9	97.7	98.1	97.8	98.2	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
<i>p</i> -Toluenethiol	98.1	98.0	98.2	98.0	98.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	97.2	97.1	97.3	97.0	96.9	Iodimetry (12)
<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene α thiol	99.2	99.4	99.3	99.5	99.0	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
2-Diethylaminoethanethiol hydrochloride	98.7	98.5	98.7	98.5	98.7	Iodimetry (12)
Toluenethiol (mixed isomers)	93.2	93.0	93.4	93.1	93.2	Iodimetry (12)
2-Butanethiol	96.9	96.7	97.0	96.8	97.1	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)

*Average of 10 determinations, average deviations were in the range of 0.3—0.5%.

MC=Monochloramine ;
DC=Dichloramine ;
MB=Monobromamine ;
DB=Dibromamine.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH *N*-HALOAMIDES

Sample	Purity%				Comparison method	Ref
	MBB*	NBA*	NCB*	NCA*		
Glutathione	98.0	98.2	98.4	98.6	98.1	Iodimetry (10)
2-Mercaptoethyl-ammonium chloride	97.9	98.0	98.2	98.4	97.8	Iodimetry (12)
2-Naphthalenethiol	99.3	99.2	99.0	99.0	99.5	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
1-Butanethiol	99.1	99.0	98.9	98.8	99.4	Acetylation (11)
Allyl thiol	94.0	93.8	93.7	93.7	94.1	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Toluene- α -thiol	98.3	98.4	98.6	98.6	98.7	Acetylation (11)
<i>p</i> -Toluenethiol	98.2	98.1	98.0	98.0	98.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene- α -thiol	98.7	98.6	98.5	98.6	99.0	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Toluenethiol (mixed isomers)	93.0	93.2	93.4	93.3	93.2	Iodimetry (12)
2-Butanethiol	97.0	96.8	96.8	96.9	97.2	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	98.2	98.1	98.0	98.1	98.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
2 Diethylaminoethanethiol hydrochloride	98.6	98.7	98.6	98.6	98.7	Iodimetry (12)
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	97.1	97.2	97.1	97.1	96.9	Iodimetry (12)
2-Mercaptoethanol	97.8	97.9	97.7	97.7	98.2	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Benzenethiol	98.9	99.0	98.8	98.8	99.4	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)
Methyl-3-mercapto-propionate	96.1	96.2	96.4	96.5	96.1	Iodimetry (12)
Thiobenzoic acid	95.0	95.3	95.2	95.2	94.8	Iodimetry (12)
1-Pentanethiol	82.1	81.9	81.8	82.0	82.4	Acetylation (11)
Mercaptoacetic acid	82.0	82.2	82.3	82.1	82.5	Iodimetry (12)
1-Propanethiol	83.8	93.6	93.7	93.6	94.0	Pb ⁴⁺ titration (9)

*Average of 10 determinations ; average deviations were in the range of 0.3-0.5%.

NBB=*N*-bromobenzamide

NBA = *N*-bromoacetamide

NCB = *N*-chlorobenzamide

NCA = *N*-chloroacetamide

 TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF XANTHATES WITH *N*-BROMO-BENZAMIDE AND *N*-BROMOACETAMIDE.

Sample	Purity %		Iodine titration (13,14)	Sulphur analysis
	NBB*	NBA*		
K Methylxanthate	96.4	96.3	96.8	97.5
Na Ethylxanthate	89.6	89.5	90.2	89.9
K <i>n</i> -Propylxanthate	99.7	99.5	99.9	100.0
K <i>n</i> -Butylxanthate	94.0	94.1	93.8	94.6
K iso-Propylxanthate	78.3	78.4	79.1	78.8
K iso-Butylxanthate	92.4	92.3	93.0	92.6
K Amylxanthate	94.6	94.5	94.3	95.0
K Iso-Amylxanthate	96.8	96.6	97.1	97.5
K Allylxanthate	93.8	93.7	94.2	94.9
K Cyclohexylxanthate	75.9	75.8	76.4	76.2
K sec-Butylxanthate	98.9	98.8	99.1	99.6
Carbon disulphide	95.1	95.2	94.8	—

*Average of 10 determinations ; relative standard deviation in the range of 0.3-0.5%

TABLE 4—INTERFERENCES IN TITRATION OF MERCAPTANS AND XANTHATES WITH N-HALOAMINES AND N-HALOAMIDES.

Sample titrated	Titrant	Compound added	Molar ratio added Compd/sample	Sample recovery (%)*
2-Mercaptoethanol	MC	Uric acid	20:1	100.1
		Carbon disulphide	54:1	101.5
		Allyl alcohol	53:1	100.8
		Glycine	37:1	100.1
		Potassium Iodide	50:1	97.2
K n-Propylxanthate	NBB	Dextrose	80:1	100.0
		Dimethylsulphoxide	42:1	99.8
		Methyl acrylate	30:1	99.4
		Dibenzyl sulphide	10:1	100.0
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	DB	Acetaldehyde	20:1	99.2
		Sodium chloride	113:1	99.9
		Acrylonitrile	136:1	98.0
K Allylxanthate	NBA	Diacetone alcohol	5:1	100.3
		Diphenyldisulphide	18:1	100.0
		Urea	40:1	100.1
		Thiophene	19:1	102.3
		Alanine	41:1	99.8
Mercaptoacetic acid	MB	Potassium bromide	5:1	102.0
		Acetone	56:1	98.5
		Propylene glycol	13:1	100.0
		Sulphosalicylic acid	9:1	103.0
		Bromobenzene	68:1	100.0

* Average of 4 determinations : % recovery takes into account the previously determined purity of the sample (Table 1, 2, 3).

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